

ORIGINAL RESEARCH**Violations of International Humanitarian Law: Political Views on Law and Human Rights**

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to analyze the form of settlement of violations of International Humanitarian Law, as well as to analyze the Legal Politics of Human Rights in view of gross international human rights violations. The normative legal method used in this research. The results of recitations or trials in international humanitarian law and international human rights are good and very important in ensuring justice for victims of human rights violations, but in the human rights judicial process it should not take a long time to make decisions on victims and their families.

Keywords: Legal Politics; Humanitarian Law; Human Rights

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1. Introduction

Attention to Human Rights is in line with the development of the era of globalization which requires recognition of universal values that are believed to be true. The universal value is the value of humanity that is carried by every human being in the world, with the recognition of these universal values, the rights of every human being must be respected. Besides being universal, human rights are also contextual, meaning that human rights appear in certain social contexts and face certain challenges. As a form of Indonesia's commitment to provide protection for human rights, in addition to the recognition in the constitution, Law No. 39 of 1999 concerning Human Rights was promulgated (Agustiartono 2006).

The roll out of reforms in Indonesia in 1998 was marked by the transfer of power from President Suharto to BJ Habibie, prompting the Indonesian people to demand an end to past human rights violations. The demand for disclosure of past human rights violations such as what happened in Indonesia by Jorge Correa is a political situation that must be faced in the transition period (Correa 2014). In

addition, the demands for the settlement of human rights cases have also attracted international attention (Arinanto 2004). Related to this, the international community wonders whether international humanitarian law has been implemented or whether the law has been ignored by the authorities, as well as what about the perpetrators of this violation of international humanitarian law (AKBAR 2017). in Indonesia itself. Human rights violations are not new, such as the cases of students being killed during demonstrations due to clashes with security forces, such as the Trisakti cases (12 May 1998), Semanggi I (13 November 1998), and Semanggi II (22-24 September 1999) International (Arinanto 2015).

Attention and pressure on the handling of gross human rights violations also occurred in the conflict in the former Yugoslavia. To try the perpetrators of war crimes and human rights violations in the former Yugoslavia, the United Nations Security Council (UNSC) through Resolution No. 827 of 1993 dated 25 May 2003 established the International Criminal Tribunal for the Former Yugoslavia (ICTY) based in The Hague, Dutch. ICTY was formed under the Statue of International